

CHARACTERISTICS OF GASTRONOMY ADVERTISING TEXTS AND ITS STUDY

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Abstract: Today, gastronomic advertising texts are becoming an important part of human life. In addition, it is worth noting that gastronomic advertising texts have formed a culture creator in society and are seen as a force that increases the demand of consumers for food products. Of course, the main influence of gastronomic advertising, whether oral or written, is the language and its internal possibilities. Gastronomic advertising texts in Uzbek, as in other languages, differ sharply from other types of texts with their specific features and methods of expression. In turn, several types of gastronomic advertising texts are classified. This article provides information about gastronomic advertising texts and their types, as well as the importance of language tools in such texts.

Key words: advertising text, gastronomic advertising, comparative-typological, pragmatic features.

In recent years, the volume of gastronomic advertising texts has been increasing. Advertising activity is analyzed from various aspects: economic, sociological, cultural, legal, psychological, socio-philosophical, linguistic, etc. Thus, marketers are primarily interested in the economic efficiency of advertising. Sociologists determine the laws of the impact of advertising on different groups of the population, taking into account their value orientations. The attention of cultural scientists is focused on advertising as a manifestation of mass culture. Lawyers will investigate advertising text that violates other administrative or legal regulations. Psychologists who study advertising pay attention to phenomena such as social perception. In philosophical works, gastronomic advertising is considered as a means of social changes that took place in the last decade. In this case, gastronomic advertising is interpreted as an important feature of modern globalization. The main direction of the linguistic study of advertising is text linguistics, its description from the point of view of the main paradigm "text - speech". Socio-cultural components also play an important role here, they can be similar and can be very different in individual cultures. Thus, the linguistic and pragmatic features of gastronomic advertising texts are excluded, some aspects specific to culture. Advertising is a very versatile phenomenon. Therefore, it is not

surprising that the interpretations of this concept and the specific definitions of the term are very different. As the study "History of Advertising" correctly states, "the existence of many definitions of the topic of interest should not confuse new, inexperienced professionals in the field of advertising - it is any complex, multifaceted, to some extent, even phenomena of universal reality" [Uchenova, 1999: Electronic resource]. Advertising occupies a boundary position between different professional fields and attracts the attention of representatives of different professions. Determining specific directions of activity in the field of advertising indicates its development to a certain extent. However, now we can say with confidence that advertising is becoming a professional activity.

Eating is one of the basic human needs and also one of the main sources of enjoyment. Knowing well that people can live without luxury goods, expensive appliances and impractical clothes, but do not want to give up delicious and cheap food, food manufacturers have long advertised one of their allies. At the same time, it was important for them to force consumers to "buy more and cook less" [Parkin, 2001: 2], that is, to turn the cult of home-cooked food into a cult that does not require special skills. or a waste of time from the housewife, because traditionally in many cultures food selection and preparation is still the prerogative of women. Although the boundaries of social roles have become increasingly blurred, the connection between food, women and the display of love remains the same. In Russia, they say that the way to a man's heart is through his stomach. If you believe the hype, it turns out that soup in a can or a stir-fry made from a plastic tube heated in the microwave is a great choice for the modern woman, whether she is working or on the Internet [Jakob, 1990: 25]. In addition to the simplicity and speed of preparation, most food advertising today is based on a number of standard concepts, for example: "naturalness". This concept is especially important for food advertising, where the word "natural" fills the semantic field. will do with the meanings "real", "healthy", "natural". Other combinations that are often found in advertising texts of the described type are various inscriptions on the packaging that emphasize the naturalness of the product. For example, "preservative-free", "GMO-free", "100%

Natural product", "without dyes", "produced on our own farm", etc. By this we mean real friendly communication, meetings of relatives and friends, which of course are accompanied by the preparation and consumption of honey and drinks together. comes together. It is important that the semantic field of the concept includes words that express the emotional state of a person during communication. It is assumed that such gatherings should be warm, cheerful, cheerful, etc. Pleasant communication, as

advertisers remember, every is always a pleasure. A friendly or family holiday fills the hearts of its participants with feelings of joy and peace.

Positive evaluations of the pleasure of eating include words such as "happiness", "sweetness", "intoxication", "pleasure" and even "happiness". "Perfection" As any advertised product claims to be the best of the best, it is clear that the concept of "perfection" is prevalent not only in food advertising, but in advertising in general. Information about high production standards and production quality is an integral attribute of consumer goods advertising, which is based on the words "excellent", "perfect", "best", "most". The linguistic conceptualization of food assumes the existence of cultural or linguistic and cultural competence as a cognitive construct that generalizes knowledge. It helps to deeply understand the essence of the cultural meaning attached to a certain language sign, as well as all the cultural attitudes and traditions of the people. The concept of "food" is a complex mental formation, in which some structural features can be identified that are partially compatible. Earlier in this work, it was repeatedly emphasized that food as a means of satisfying one of the basic human needs is a very unusual product from the point of view of the advertiser and especially the producer of advertising [Parkin, 2011]. It is very important for every day man, he cannot exist without it, and therefore it is not so difficult to advertise it. You just need to produce a high-quality product, and it will be in demand without any additional effort or financial investment. In addition, some companies structure their advertising strategy in such a way as to emphasize as clearly as possible, they do not at all tend to make their products look unique or original. Of course, they are right in a way. Especially if the brand initially targets traditional consumers who have bought the same product in the same package for years. It is not surprising that there are milk brands "Simply" or "Tasty". However, practice shows that many modern consumers pay attention to many factors, in particular, brand awareness, when choosing food products. Also, when we talk about a new product, but a daily demand product. For example, yogurt or corn flakes. Everyday life is already full of challenges, so no one wants to complicate it by not being able to make choices. Coming to the store, customers naively believe that they can make purchasing decisions themselves. In fact, they unknowingly often follow the instructions given by advertising professionals: "try it", "upgrade", "dive in", "feel", etc. in other words - "buy". Behind these concepts, we can learn the true essence of advertising texts.

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